

Teacher training workshop

The teacher training workshops will be facilitated by teachers who participated in the pilot study or are members of the teachers' network. They will use resources provided in the IHC secondary school resources, including the schedule below, [the presentations](#) listed in the schedule, a [Teachers' guide](#), and [printouts](#) that will be provided in a workshop binder. Members of the research team will provide the facilitators with the workshop materials and review the materials with them. This approach to teacher training is like the approach normally used in Kenya, Rwanda, and Uganda to introduce changes to the curriculum.

Teacher training workshop schedule and facilitator notes

Notes for facilitators

- Adjust the suggested times as needed, depending on when the workshop will start and end each day, how many days the workshop will last, and how much time you feel you need for each session.
- Send the agenda to participants in advance and instructions to access the BeSmartHealth website before the workshop, so that the resources are installed on their computer or smartphone.
- Make sure everyone brings a computer or smartphone that they have used to access the BeSmartHealth website before the workshop. They should, if possible, open all the lessons (so that they are downloaded, in case of problems with the Internet at the workshop). Teachers who plan on using the projector version of the lessons should download the slides, if possible, since those are not automatically saved.
- Hand out workbooks at the workshop.
- Review all the presentations before the workshop.
- Download the presentations as PowerPoint files, in case of a poor Internet connection.
- For the sessions on each lesson, do some in the plenary / large group (e.g., Lesson 1) and others in small groups. When relevant, model teaching lessons or teaching strategies that are more difficult.
- Make sure that participants have time to review and discuss each lesson. The presentations are intended as introductions and should not take up the entire session. They should be shortened, if necessary, to allow more time for the teachers to review and discuss the lessons – assuming there is an adequate Internet connection, or the teachers have opened/downloaded the lessons prior to the workshop.
- If it is feasible/practical to have a 3-day workshop, you could give participants more time to prepare for teaching the lessons, e.g., make the sessions that focus on each of the 10 lessons longer.

Time	Minutes	Presentations	Notes for facilitators
Day 1			
08:00	30	1. Introduction	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Facilitators introduce themselves ● Ask participants to introduce themselves in breakout groups and when they say something
	30	2. Overview of the lessons	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Slides 23-25: Unless you think teachers might be interested in the curriculum in other countries, you can delete or skip the two slides that are not for your country
	60	3. Introduction to the learning resources	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Slide 2 has an embedded link to a 3-minute video. However, to show the video, your computer must be connected to a speaker, and you need a good Internet connection. To open the video in a downloaded PowerPoint file, click on the image. ● Give the participants time to explore the resources when you get to Slide 8 ● Suggest that they look at each of the things listed on the slide <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ You might want to demonstrate each of those things by opening and projecting besmarthealth.org ○ You might want to have them explore besmarthealth.org in pairs or small groups and to help each other ● Tell the participants they can ask for help if they have any problems
	30	Break	
10:30	45	4. Teaching strategies	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Slide 8 is a demonstration of buzz groups. Give participants about 2 minutes to discuss. Get feedback (responses to the questions) from some of the participants. You can let them know that when you go through the individual lessons, you will use small groups ● Slide 10 is a demonstration of class discussion. The idea is for the participants to answer the questions, not for the facilitator to answer them. If participants ask questions, try asking the participants what they think, rather than answering the question yourself ● Slides 13-15 are a demonstration of using response cards. Give the participants feedback, since they should not be able to see each other's responses, and allow time for discussion, e.g., ask what they like or do not like about using response cards
	45	5. Teaching tips	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Slide 14: Give the participants time to try using the resources offline and to download a presentation and/or a PDF file
	60	Lunch	

Time	Minutes	Presentations	Notes for facilitators
13:00	40	6. Lesson 1	
	40	7. Lesson 2	
	40	8. Lesson 3	
	30	Break	
15:30	40	9. Lesson 4	
	40	10. Lesson 5	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> You might want to move this session to day 2 and have the participants start planning for the term at the end of day 1 (see presentation 16. Preparing for the term) and then come back to planning for the term again, after the session on Lesson 10.
16:40	20	Wrap-up for the day (no presentation)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Ask if there are any questions Give information about dinner and start time tomorrow Encourage them to read the background for each of the lessons
Day 2			
08:00	40	11. Lesson 6	
	40	12. Lesson 7	
	40	13. Lesson 8	
	30	Break	
10:30	40	14. Lesson 9	
	40	15. Lesson 10	
	40	16. Preparing for the term	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Slide 5: Give the participants time to start filling in a schedule for the term Tell them to continue preparing for teaching the lessons if they don't need the time to work on their schedule
	60	Lunch	
13:30	60	17. Other relevant resources	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Slide 12: Give participants time to explore the resources
	40	18. Development and evaluation	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> The research fellows may want to do this presentation, since it is not about teacher training, and is primarily about the randomised trial Slide 14: Give them time to fill in a teacher evaluation form. Add screen shots and link to the form to the presentation Add slides for baseline data collection, if you plan on collecting that during the workshop
	20	19. Wrap-up	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Give them time to finish preparing for the lessons if there is time at the end of the day Prepare a workshop evaluation form, add a slide with a screenshot and link, and have teachers complete it
15:30	30	Break	